

PSYCHOPROFLATIC MEASURES TO PREVENT PSYCHOSOMATIC (MENTAL-PHYSICAL) DISEASES AT SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the causes of psychosomatic diseases in school-age students, their impact on physical and mental health, and the importance of psychopreventive measures for their prevention. It also recommends psychopreventive measures to prevent psychosomatic diseases, including optimizing the school environment, providing psychological support to students, and effective cooperation with parents and teachers. A systematic and comprehensive approach to preventing the spread of psychosomatic diseases in schools is analyzed.

Despite general digitization, teaching and learning remains an analog process today. Modern teaching research is increasingly focusing on the aspect of the teacher-student relationship. Since the quality of this relationship is one of the important factors of educational effectiveness, it needs to be constantly developed.

Introduction

In recent years, problems related to mental and physical health have been increasing among schoolchildren. As a result of stress, overload, fear and internal conflicts, children experience psychosomatic symptoms such as headaches, heart palpitations, abdominal pain, insomnia. These conditions reduce the quality of education, attention and social interaction of the child.

Our republic has chosen its own path of socio-economic and political development. We are striving to build our state on the basis of modern democratic principles, along with the best traditions of our ancient statehood. Our achievements today are, in a sense, the foundation of a great future. Therefore, no matter who we are or what field we work in, we should not forget that we are involved in the work of educating and bringing up mature people. We all have a sense of responsibility. This issue is related to the fate of the future generation. In this regard, it is very appropriate to mention the following thoughts of our president:

“...We will raise young people to be independent and logical thinkers, possessing noble qualities, based on modern knowledge and experience, national and universal values.”¹

¹ <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/4057>. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoevning Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi 29.12.2020

The bright future of our republic is connected with the issues of educating well-rounded people. After all, the development of society is unimaginable without the development of the individual. The rational implementation of spiritual and educational work is of paramount importance in strengthening the foundations of our independence, in the development of our country and in the transformation of Uzbekistan into a great state. Because the fate of development is decided by people who are spiritually mature, possess modern knowledge, have a strong will, have a strong faith, and have deep thoughts

The issue of educating young people, who are the future of our country's development, as fully developed and spiritually mature people, is a strategic issue for our state. Considering that the vast majority of the population of Uzbekistan is made up of young people under the age of 30, educating this young generation as fully developed and spiritually mature people, and educating and training them so that they can compete in all aspects with the youth of developed countries, is one of the urgent issues of today.

One of the main goals of the reforms being carried out by our state today is to educate the younger generation as fully developed individuals in both mental and physical aspects. This requires us to take preventive measures to prevent physical diseases associated with the mental state of students. This is a particularly common problem among school-age children. These diseases are associated with the child's mental state, stress and anxiety, which negatively affect their health and complicate the educational process

Causes of psychosomatic diseases

Psychosomatic diseases in school-age children are mainly caused by the following factors:

- Constant mental stress: exams, relationships with classmates, pressure from teachers.
- Family problems: conflicts between parents, neglect, stress in the family.
- Problems in the social environment: separation from friends, discrimination or violence.
- Personal factors: the child's specific mental state, personal worries and concerns

Symptoms of psychosomatic diseases

These diseases are often manifested by physical symptoms: headaches, gastrointestinal disorders, heart palpitations, fatigue, muscle pain, etc. However, their true cause may be psychological, which is why their identification and treatment requires the cooperation of psychologists and doctors.

During school, children are faced with many stressful situations: exams, relationships with classmates, pressure from teachers, and family problems. These factors can lead to the development of psychosomatic diseases. To prevent such diseases at school, it is necessary to reduce mental stress, provide psychological support to students, and work in partnership with parents and teachers. It is important that psychopreventive measures are systematically organized and effectively implemented.

The following measures are important for preventing psychosomatic diseases in the school environment:

1. Creating a mentally healthy environment - a warm, supportive atmosphere in the classroom.
2. Providing emotional release - reducing stress for children through music, drawing, and physical exercises.

3. Training for teachers - improving their skills in understanding the child's psyche and early detection of stress.
4. Regular conversations with a psychologist - monthly monitoring of the child's mental state
5. Cooperation with parents - creating an equally supportive environment for the child at home and at school
6. Active rest during breaks - improving mental state through physical activity and positive emotions.

Therefore, it is important to focus on psychopreventive measures to prevent psychosomatic diseases in schools.

Psychopreventive measures include:

- developing stress management skills in students;
- organizing regular psychological counseling and training;
- monitoring the mental state in close cooperation with parents and teachers;
- creating a comfortable and safe environment at school;
- strengthening mental health through involvement in sports and artistic activities.

Also, school psychologists and teachers should regularly monitor the mental state of students and provide early assistance in problem situations. This will prevent the development of psychosomatic diseases and improve the health and academic success of students.

Psychological support and counseling

Regular individual and group counseling of students by school psychologists.

Early identification of mental stress in children by a school psychologist

The teacher should use a gentle, motivating approach to such children during the lesson

Organize training to reduce stress and teach problem-solving skills.

Also, prevention is effective when specialists work together.

Creating an environment of social and psychological support for students

Creating a friendly, supportive environment at school.

Preventing violence and discrimination.

Collaboration with parents and teachers

Inform parents about mental health, provide information on ways to reduce stress.

Train teachers to identify children's mental state and provide them with psychological support.

Optimize the school environment

Keep the workload moderate, give students breaks.

Pay more attention to sports, art and other creative activities.

Early detection and rehabilitation

Refer to psychologists and doctors when psychosomatic symptoms appear. Use medical and psychological rehabilitation programs if necessary

Conclusion

Psychosomatic diseases are widespread among school-age children, and a systematic, comprehensive approach is necessary to prevent them. Effective implementation of psychopreventive measures reduces mental stress, strengthens the physical and mental health of students, and as a result, increases educational success. Schools, parents, and society must

work together to ensure the healthy and happy growth of children. Prevention of psychosomatic diseases requires systematic and effective implementation of psychopreventive measures, the active participation of all school participants - students, teachers, and parents. Creating a positive psychological environment at school, reducing stress, and taking into account the emotional needs of each child are the main conditions for raising a healthy generation.

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